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Atmospheric factors related to the production of anti-allergic drugs in Japan

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Abstract

Background: It is known that atmospheric conditions such as photochemical oxidants and meteorological factors are closely related to the induction of allergic symptoms. Therefore, they may be relevant to the demand for anti-allergic drugs and, consequently, to their production.

Methods: To clarify the relationship between anti-allergic drugs production in Japan and atmospheric conditions such as photochemical oxidants, ambient temperature and relative humidity, correlation analysis and multiple linear regression analysis were performed.

Results: Stepwise multiple regression analysis with anti-allergic drugs production as the objective variable, smoking rate, photochemical oxidants, ambient temperature and relative humidity as explanatory variables, revealed that photochemical oxidants and relative humidity were significant independent variables.

Conclusion: Present study suggests that atmospheric conditions such as photochemical oxidants and relative humidity may be associated with the anti-allergic drugs production.

Keywords: anti-allergic drugs production; photochemical oxidants; ambient temperature; relative humidity

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1. Introduction

Atmospheric conditions such as photochemical oxidants and meteorological factors are closely associated with the onset of allergic reactions [1], and may therefore be linked to the demand for anti-allergic drugs and, consequently, their production. The author investigated the relationship between the production of anti-allergic drugs in Japan and atmospheric conditions.

2. Methods

2.1. Annual production of anti-allergic drugs

Data since 2010 were from Statistics of Production by Pharmaceutical Industry conducted by Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare (https://www.e-stat.go.jp/statsearch/files?page=1&toukei=00450151&result_page=1). Data before 2010 were from “KokuminEisei no doko”, edition for 19912009: Kosei Tokei Kyokai (Health, Labour and Welfare Statistics Association).

2.2. Annual average values of photochemical oxidants

The annual average values of photochemical oxidants (maximum hourly values during the day) were provided by the Ministry of the Environment. (https://www.env.go.jp/press/press_03287.html)

2.3. Meteorological conditions

The annual average values of ambient temperature and relative humidity by prefecture were from Social Indicators by Prefecture. The values were downloaded from e-Stat (<https://www.e-stat.go.jp/dbview?sid=0000010102>). The arithmetic average of ambient temperature and relative humidity for the 47 prefectures was used as the average for Japan as a whole.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Correlation analysis and stepwise multiple linear regression analysis were performed to clarify the relationship between the annual amount of anti-allergic drugs production and the annual average values of photochemical oxidants, ambient temperature, and relative humidity. A p value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. Changes in annual production of anti-allergic drugs.

The annual production of anti-allergic drugs increased from 1991 to around 2000, then plateaued and began to decline after 2015.

3.2. Changes in photochemical oxidants and meteorological conditions

Photochemical oxidants have been increasing until around 2001, then plateaued and have been declining slightly since 2015 (Figure 2).

The annual average value of ambient temperature has shown a slight but significant upward trend, while relative humidity showed a slight downward trend until around 2007 and has since shown an upward trend (Figure 3, 4).

3.3. Correlation analysis and stepwise multiple linear regression analysis

The results of the correlation analysis are shown in Table 1. Photochemical oxidants showed a significant positive correlation with the annual production of anti-allergic drugs, while relative humidity showed a significant negative correlation with the annual production of anti-allergic drugs. Furthermore, photochemical oxidants showed a significant negative correlation with relative humidity and a significant positive correlation with ambient temperature (Figure 5).

Stepwise multiple regression analysis with the annual production of anti-allergic drugs as the objective variable, photochemical oxidants, ambient temperature and relative humidity as explanatory variables, revealed that relative humidity and photochemical oxidants significant independent variables (Table 2).

Figure 1. Changes in production of anti-allergic drugs from 1991 to 2023.

Figure 2. Changes in photochemical oxidants from 1991 to 2023.

Figure 3. Changes in relative humidity from 1991 to 2023.

Figure 4. Changes in ambient temperature from 1991 to 2023.

Figure 5. Relations between anti-allergic drugs production, photochemical oxidants, relative humidity and ambient temperature.

Table 1. Correlation analysis between annual production of anti-allergic drugs and photochemical oxidants and meteorological conditions. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

	Anti-allergic drugs	Photochemical oxidants	Relative Humidity	Temperature
Anti-allergic drugs		0.494**	-0.600***	-0.077
Photochemical oxidants	0.494**		-0.343*	0.442**
Relative Humidity	-0.600***	-0.343*		0.247
Temperature	-0.077	0.442**	0.247	

Table 2. Stepwise multiple regression analysis with annual production of anti-allergic drugs as the objective variable, photochemical oxidants, ambient temperature and relative humidity as explanatory variables.

Independent variables	Estimated regression coefficient B	95% confidence interval		Partial regression coefficient β	Cumulative R ²	P-value
		Lower bound	Upper bound			
Intercept	869005.021	208527.556	1529482.5	-	-	0.012
Relative Humidity	-13142856.000	-21038.269	-5247.442	-0.488	0.360	0.002
Photochemical oxidants	5449158.4	544771.459	10353545	0.326	0.454	0.031

4. Discussion

Since atmospheric conditions such as photochemical oxidants and meteorological factors are closely related to the induction of allergic symptoms, they may be relevant to the demand for anti-allergic drugs and, consequently, to their production. Therefore, the authors investigated the relationship between annual production of anti-allergic drugs and the annual average values of photochemical oxidants, temperature, and relative humidity. Stepwise multiple regression analysis revealed that relative humidity and photochemical oxidants were significant correlates. However, regression analysis results have limitations in that they cannot prove causality. Relative humidity, a significantly negative independent variable, had a partial R² of 0.360, indicating its contribution to the variance of anti-allergic drugs production. Furthermore, the cumulative R² of photochemical oxidants, another significant independent variable, was 0.454, suggesting its contribution to anti-allergic drugs production is not negligible. While the average annual change in relative humidity is only a few percent, it is a significant change compared to the dry season and changes in precipitation throughout the year. During the dry season, asthma patients' mucous membranes become dry and sensitive, making them more susceptible to attacks. [2] Additionally, several studies have shown a negative correlation between outdoor relative humidity and the prevalence of type 1 allergies, including asthma, hay fever, and eczema. Low humidity increases pollen dispersal [3-6] and facilitates its transport in urban areas [7-9]. Furthermore, in urban areas, allergens deposited on pavement [10] and buildings can be repeatedly resuspended. Low humidity also weakens the skin barrier [11-13]. On the other hand, high humidity increases hygroscopicity, which can affect pollen deposition rate and transport [14]. Humidity also has a significant effect on photochemical reactions [15]. Photochemical oxidant, 98% of which is ozone [16]. High humidity causes ozone decomposition [17], [18], [19]. In fact, this study also showed a significant negative correlation between annual average relative humidity and photochemical oxidants. Photochemical oxidants are potent oxidative stressors, generating reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as superoxide (O₂⁻) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), which enhance inflammation and cause asthma symptoms [20]. ROS also cause skin barrier dysfunction and inflammation, leading to skin allergic diseases [21]. These symptoms are often precursors to other allergic diseases, such as asthma and food allergies [22]. From the above, it can be seen that relative humidity and photochemical oxidants are closely related to the induction of allergies, and may therefore be linked to the production of anti-allergic drugs.

5. Conclusion

This study suggests that atmospheric conditions, such as photochemical oxidants and relative humidity, may be associated with the production of anti-allergic drugs. This result suggests that atmospheric environmental conditions are closely related to allergies.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this work.

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